

SHREKSPEARE OR SHAKESPEARE GONE MANGA. AN EXTREME READING OF WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE

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ABSTRACT: Shrekspeare or Shakespeare gone Manga. An Extreme Reading of William Shakespeare.

Shakespeare's plays were written with a view to be performed on stage, in front of an audience. Never have they been intended for being read by the audience. It seems that the only people who were meant to read the script were the very actors. And one finds no stage directions for the sole reason that the Bard himself was in place simply telling the actors what to do on stage. Reading Shakespeare in its original form is about 10% translating it from a language no one speaks anymore¹.

The present paper presents things the other way round, namely the outcome of modernity re-writing Shakespeare in manga - a language people of his time would have had to re-interpret and translate, at least 10%.

Keywords: *fragmentation, consumer culture, high culture, manga.*

Japan's worldwide notorious postwar economy exports, namely automobiles and steel, are now exceeded by the manga exports². *Manga* are comics created in Japan, or by Japanese creators in the Japanese language, conforming to a style developed in Japan in the late 19th century. They have a long and complex pre-history in earlier Japanese art. It seems that manga is the fastest-growing comics market for Western readers. Researchers point out that “manga have become the largest segment of translated comics in the Western world”³. Manga discourse—not just the reading of manga but

1 “Thou” means you. “Ere” means “before.” “Dost” means “does.” Etc., Lanier, 2022, p. 105;

2 Jüngst, Heike, *Translating Manga. Comics in Translation*, Federico Zanettin (ed.), Manchester, St. Jerome, UK, 2018, p. 50.

3 Ibid. p. 52.

the viewing of anime (Japanese animation) and participation in fan-based activities such as online chat groups, conventions, cosplay⁴ and fan-fiction—provides a community for young manga readers that is in many ways “incomprehensible” to their parents.⁵

Although the reading of manga in Japan is not exclusively reserved to youth culture, manga exports from Japan, as well as manga produced in the European and American markets, are especially appealing to young people as a means of going against the established values of high culture. A very good and novel example of this is the “adoption” of Shakespeare by manga artists who thus provide a totally unique “interplay between two cultural systems—high and pop culture—that operate in parallel realms, two bodies of reference, sets of cultural institutions, canons of aesthetic standards, modes of constructing cultural authority”⁶.

Long before globalization⁷ was coined as term and multidimensional phenomenon, about half a millennium ago, people were beginning to live in a global village where everybody knew... Shakespeare. When the Bard of Avon was only 7 the world was already shrinking. Not just because trade was bringing the continents closer every day, but also due to the cultural exchanges that were multiplying between Europe, the Americas and even Asia. English was taking its first steps towards getting the *lingua franca* status it has today. So the word got out and Great Will gained wide notoriety on all populated continents: moreover, starting in his own lifetime, Hamlet began to speak French and a number of other European vernaculars. Somebody was really *shaking the spear* globally!

We now live in a world gone globalized economically, but fragmented culturally⁸. However, there is a huge renewal of interest for cultural and

4 Fans dressing up as their favourite manga characters.

5 Allison, Anne, *The Japan Fad in Global Youth Culture and Millennial Capitalism*. Mechademia 1: *Emerging Worlds of Anime and Manga*, Frenchy Lunning (ed.), Minneapolis, MN., University of Minnesota Press, 2016, pp. 11–21.

6 Lanier, Douglas, *Shakespeare and Modern Popular Culture*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2022, p. 137.

7 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Globalization and its effect on religion”, *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință*, Mihnea Costoiu, Liviu-Bogdan Ciucă, Nelu Burcea (eds.), Les Arcs, France, Iarsic, 2014, vol.1,nr.1, pp.532-541.

8 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Current Values of Education and Culture”, in *Proceedings of the 23th International RAIS Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities*, August 15-16, 2021, Princeton, NJ, United States of America, pp. 87-92.

civilizational⁹ identities going on. And apparently Shakespeare himself went Manga in the process. Manga has emerged as one of the newest and most fashionable ways to remake Shakespeare for popular culture. The graphic reworkings of Shakespeare's volumes provide a translation that keeps this "interplay between two cultural systems" dynamic and available for the reader.

Therefore, *Manga Shakespeare* represents a new interpretive challenge that makes the great poet of the Western literary canon get transposed into a popular modern Japanese graphic art form. As you like it, if you please. In *Manga Shakespeare*, specialists read an annulment of distinction between high culture and consumer culture, a contest of authority and the tendency to resist the established values of high culture¹⁰. The king is dead, long live... Shrekspeare!?

The UK-based *Manga Shakespeare* series¹¹ manages the commercial interests of youth culture alongside the academic investment of high culture, setting these two "Shakespeares" side by side on the page. Although the British *Manga Shakespeare* is not the only graphic adaptation of Shakespeare's plays, it is definitely one of the most artistically interesting and has gained tremendous financial success as a published graphic series. Since its beginning in 2007, it has proudly produced fourteen volumes of abridged manga versions of Shakespeare's plays.

The *Manga Shakespeare* collection aims at engaging a segment of the readership market that might not be normally interested in Shakespeare. Therefore, this graphic "reinvention" of Shakespeare is seen by many educators, parents and students as the ideal way to help struggling young readers "get Shakespeare."

Reviewers of *Manga Shakespeare* have emphasized the medium as notably appropriate for the adaptation of Shakespeare. A reviewer in *The Observer* writes, "This 'manga Shakespeare' hybrid is unlikely – but makes

9 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, "Aspects of Biblical Philosophy on the Development of World Civilizations", *Scientia Moralitas. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* 8 (2023), nr.1, pp. 62-79.

10 Lanier, Douglas, *Shakespeare and Modern Popular Culture*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2022, p. 137.

11 Hulbert, Jennifer, Kevin J. Wetmore, Jr., and Robert L. York, eds., *Dude, Where's My Bard? Reducing, Translating, and Referencing Shakespeare for Youth: An Introduction. Shakespeare and Youth Culture*. New York, Palgrave Macmillan, 2006, pp.1–41.

absolute sense . . . [it] shares similarities with Shakespeare's theatre, relying heavily on recurring image and highly expressive gestures."

One critic in the Financial Times even puts forward that "A cartoon version of Shakespeare is in some ways truer to the original than reading the text alone; the visual element was always supposed to be part of the experience."

The Independent on Sunday measures the success of Manga Shakespeare with the innovative adaptation of *Romeo and Juliet* by Baz Luhrmann: "This new series does in book form what film director Baz Luhrmann did on screen – make Shakespeare cool and accessible to a younger generation... [the] artists use the dynamic flow of manga to give Shakespeare's plots an addictive page turning energy."

But it seems that, above all, critics have highlighted the emotional appeal of Manga Shakespeare as being among the most exhilarating characteristics of this pop-culture adaptation. A reviewer in *The Times* acknowledges "how vividly manga techniques and pacing can convey motion and emotion"; and yet another reviewer of Manga Shakespeare comments that "manga is a dynamic, emotional and cinematic medium easily absorbed by the eye. Its attractive art and simple storytelling methods enthuse readers to approach Shakespeare's work in the way he intended – as entertainment."¹²

In conclusion to our survey of Manga Shakespeare it would seem that manga is a very suitable medium for depicting characters as popular as Shakespeare's characters. What is intriguing in the Manga Shakespeare volumes is the way we are drawn towards emotional participation in the story, by the characters' faces and by the other signals of expressiveness, at the same time as we are drawn away from that participation through the appearance on the page of Shakespeare's lines, the language and formal elements of the text, now "mangafied."¹³ In reading Manga Shakespeare, one can come across a lively interchange between high and pop culture that captivates the reader, brightening up the sometimes equivocal cultural site of meaning that we call Shakespeare.

12 For quotations in this paragraph, see the Press Archives on the SelfMadeHero website: http://www.selfmadehero.com/manga_shakespeare/publicity.html.

13 Grande, Troni, "Manga Shakespeare and the Hermeneutic Problems of 'Double Access'", *Queen City Comics* [Online], 2010, Available at http://ourspace.uregina.ca/bitstream/handle/10294/3091/QueenCityComics-3-Troni_Grande.pdf?sequence=1 [accessed June 23, 2024].

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